

FEATURES OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS OF ECONOMIC ACCOUNTING OF MATERIAL AND TECHNICAL ASSETS

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Abstract. *The use of information technology in the educational process leads to the implementation of the principles of differential and individual approach to teaching, the teacher allows each student to work independently with teaching materials on a new topic in the classroom. Students will be able to familiarizethemselves with the new material based on the given scheme. The use of information technology also creates opportunities for distance learning. The use of computer technology in the educational process helps to improve the quality of independent learning, a creative approach to the educational process, the acquisition of newknowledge. An example is the sequence of basic concepts of algorithmic steps required to master the topic "Post theorem and its results".*

Keywords: *computer training, information technology, computer technology, quality of education, technology, e-textbook, e-learning manual.*

INTRODUCTION

Testing programs are designed to check and evaluate the quality of knowledge. They tell the student: to enter the answer as close as possible to the generally accepted form; save, collect, document and perform statistical analysis of inspection results; regardless of the form of the answer and syntactic (sentence structure) literacy, it should allow to get an adequate assessment. Information systems are programs designed to store and display a variety of educational information, such as a reference book. In these programs, educational material is placed in a hierarchical order, and it is possible to quickly search for information based on various symbols. They provide access, storage and reproduction of context information. Video computer teaching technology is a technology that encourages students' active learning and knowledge acquisition processes. This technology makes it possible to show the verbal and visual forms of educational information together, to adapt the teaching process to the goals. When students are taught individually with a computer, they cannot perform communicative activities in classes, besides, the heuristic aspect of problem-based teaching disappears. Viewing the video-computer model of teaching as an open system, other traditional means of teaching can be added to it. Of course, the weight of verbal-visual and pictorial information may change in each individual case. All this depends on the content and features of computer and video technology imaging tools and the didactic goals to be achieved in learning this topic. Currently, computers are used in the education system mainly in four areas:

- as an object of study;
- as technical means of teaching;
- in education management;
- in scientific and pedagogical research.

DISCUSSION

There are many advantages of computer-based teaching: the time required for students to develop certain skills is reduced; the number of practice tasks increases; the pace of work of

students accelerates; as a result of requiring active control by the computer, the student becomes an educational subject; it becomes possible to model and directly demonstrate processes that are difficult for students to observe and observe; it becomes possible to provide the lesson with remote resources using communication tools; communication with the computer takes the character of a didactic game, and with this, students' motivation for educational activities increases, etc. In the process of computer-based education, education is organized, managed, and controlled according to the relationship between the student and the computer. Organization of computer-based education - establishing a connection between the student and the educational material by means of a computer. Education is designed to create a connection between the student and the learning material. Organization of students' educational work, stimulation of their activity is modeled on the basis of appropriate tools. Many electronic educational materials intended for use in the educational process have been created, such as electronic textbooks, electronic study guides, educational software tools, etc. They provide a certain effectiveness in education due to the presence of features such as controllability, interactive methods, elements of artificial intelligence, emotional flexibility. The use of computers in the educational process allows:

- forms students' need to know;
- activates students' cognitive activity;
- increases students' interest in learning science;
- increases enthusiasm for learning to work with a computer;
- introduces modern methods of scientific knowledge of the world related to the use of computers;
- increases the student's level of individuality in education;
- develops students' creativity;
- ensures variety of content of materials;
- expands the range of educational materials used in education;
- strengthens demonstration in education;
- students' self-control, that is, it expands the factors of the assessment process, etc.

Principles of computer education: -scientificity -systematicity and sequence - demonstrability - individualization of students' activities - connection of theory with practice - comprehensibility - ensuring interdisciplinarity and intradiscipline connection - connection of science with life - activation of cognitive activity - teaching to research Organization, preparation of educational process of pedagogical, computer and information technologies, provision of scientific and methodical materials, implementation of educational process, it is expressed in a holistic system that consists in evaluating the quality of educational results. Programmable technologies of education are technologies that enable independent acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities with the help of educational devices based on specially developed programs. Programmed material consists of a relatively small set of educational information presented in a certain logical sequence. There are five main principles of programmable learning: - a certain hierarchy of a set of control devices. The teacher is at the highest level of teaching management. Science provides an initial general guide and shows the right way in non-standard complex situations of teaching. - the principle of organizing the educational process management system in the form of a cycle using feedback for each step (action) of educational activity.

Feedback is necessary for the teacher to make corrections 80 (correction), and for the student to understand the learning material. External feedback is used for correction. Such a

connection is made by the control devices conducting the teaching process, or by the teacher. Internal feedback serves students to independently correct the results and character of their educational activities. - the principle of a step-by-step technological process in opening and transferring educational material. In this case, the educational material in the program will be made up of separate, independent, but interconnected and small-sized information and educational tasks that help to effectively acquire knowledge, skills and abilities. The step of the training program is made up of the rules for performing positive and negative feedback information and learning actions, that is, three interconnected links (frames) are included in the content of the step: information, feedback action and check A set of step-by-step learning actions (procedures) located in a certain order forms a training program. This set is the basis of programmed teaching technology. - individual content and management principle in teaching. According to this principle, each student is offered an appropriately oriented informational process and is given the opportunity to study at a pace that corresponds to his ability to absorb knowledge. - use of special technical means for transferring programmed educational material.

THE RESULT

Computerization of mathematics education processes, the use of special software packages in experimental mathematics (Rosamund Sutherland), the informational environment of mathematics education (David Tall), the role of cognitive tools in mathematics education (Tommy Dreyfus), reference to modern electronic educational literature requirements and their use in educational processes were researched by conditions, goals and tasks (Gerhard Holland).

Teaching technology may include the following programs: linear program; branched program; adaptive program; generalized program; program-algorithm; modular training program; the program of full mastery of knowledge. A linear program consists of small blocks of training information with control tasks. In a linear program, the student goes to the next step when the answer to this step of information is correct, and when the answer is incorrect, he returns to this step, that is, he relearns the initial information. need In the networked program, when the answer is incorrect, the student is given additional educational information that allows him to complete the control task, give the correct answer, and move to the next step of the educational information. The adaptive program allows the student to choose the level of complexity of the new educational material, to change it as he mastered it, to refer to reference literature, dictionaries, manuals. The generalized program includes fragments of linear, branched and adaptive programs.

The program-algorithm determines the sequential order of theoretical and practical operations. It can be both an independent training program and a part of another training program. Algorithm refers to giving clear and clear instructions to the performer on the execution of a sequence of actions aimed at achieving the specified goal or solving the problem. Algorithms can be given orally, on the basis of a table, and in the form of a block diagram. A spoken algorithm relies on natural language support to describe words and sentences based on natural language features. Algorithm presentation on the basis of a table serves to express it in the form of a table and calculation formulas. Algorithm representation in a block diagram is a method that means that the algorithm is represented using geometric shapes called blocks. The sequence between the blocks and the lines connecting them make up the block diagram.

For example, the algorithmic steps required to master the topic of Post's theorem and its corollaries may be as follows in the form of a sequence of key concepts:

1. Boolean functions.

2. Functions that store 0.
3. Functions that preserve 1.
4. Secondary functions.
5. Functions secondary to itself.
6. Yegalkin sum.
7. Linear functions.
8. Monotonic functions.
9. Post theorem.

The stepwise logical structure of a certain text is called a logical algorithm. The logical algorithm serves as the main guide to achieving the goal in studying the material, that is, understanding the content of the material. At the same time, the text structure itself is considered an algorithm.

CONCLUSION

Algorithmization of education - determination of ways to solve educational problems and development of an algorithm for their mastery by students. In this sense, algorithmization is a didactic principle of the content of the educational material, the order of the student's activity, and the development of their thinking ability. Video computer teaching technology is a technology that encourages students' active learning and knowledge acquisition processes.

It is known that currently the President of our country attaches great importance to the field of education and has signed a number of decisions. Teaching science to students using advanced pedagogical technologies is the basis of ensuring the implementation of decisions. A number of scientific researches have been conducted in this direction. This technology makes it possible to show the verbal and visual forms of educational information together, to adapt the teaching process to the goals. When students are taught individually with a computer, they cannot perform communicative activities in classes, besides, the heuristic aspect of problem-based teaching disappears. Scientific research on mathematics, work on the application of pedagogical technologies to education was carried out in the article.

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